

Cultivating Students' Numeracy Through Math-Stery Intervention

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The purpose of this study was to determine the efficacy of a Math-stery intervention program implemented at a public high school in Laguna, Philippines, for students who achieved slow or very low score on the conducted numeracy skills pretest. The Math-stery intervention program utilized contextualized/localized intervention materials and digital integration with the participants. The quasi-experimental single group design was used in this investigation. The researchers selected participants using a purposive sampling strategy. 39 students in Grade 9 and 37 students in Grade 8 were enrolled in their study from 2020 to 2021. The researchers employed a standardized and reliable instrument with a pretest and posttest of 40 items each. Before completing the pretest and posttest, as well as administering Math-stery Intervention, the researchers obtained clearance from the school principal. Additionally, they obtained parental authorization for their children to engage in the program and take the tests. The mean and standard deviation were used to determine the level of numeracy skill performance on pretest and posttest; the Wilcoxon signed rank test was used to determine the difference between the students' pretest and posttest performances; and the Mann-Whitney U-test was used to determine the difference between the students' pretest and posttest performances according to their sex and grade level. The findings indicated that most male learners achieved low (45 or 90%) and very low levels (5 or 10%). The majority of Grade 8 (35 or 95%) and 9 (35 or 90%) participants achieved a very low score, while Grade 8 (2 or 5%) and of Grade 9 (4 or 10%) participants achieved a low score. Females ($\bar{x}=14.96$) had a higher performance in the pretest than males ($\bar{x}=13.66$). Additionally, females ($\bar{x}=26.04$) had a higher performance in the posttest than males ($\bar{x}=25.04$). Pretest results indicated that participants in Grade 8 ($\bar{x}=14.35$) had a higher performance than those in Grade 9 ($\bar{x}=13.87$). In the posttest, Grade 9 ($\bar{x}=25.49$) participants had a higher performance than Grade 8 ($\bar{x}=25.37$) participants. The posttest performance ($\bar{x}=25.38$) is greater than the pretest ($\bar{x}=14.11$). There was no statistically significant difference in respondents' numeracy skill performance by sex [pretest ($Z=-1.776$, $p=0.076$) and grade level [pretest ($Z=-0.581$, $p=0.561$) and posttest ($Z=-0.126$, $p=0.900$)]. Additionally, there was a significant difference in pretest and posttest performance across respondents ($Z=-7.598$, $p=0.001$). It was very clear that the number of students who struggled with whole numbers, fractions, decimals, and integers had reduced. The intervention materials and activities developed and implemented by the researchers in this program were determined to be effective as evidenced by the students' good outcomes. The researchers determined that the Math-stery intervention program was effective.

Keywords: *Math-stery, Intervention, Numeracy, Mathematics*